

From social interactions to transactions: investigating South African Facebook users' intention to shop on Facebook

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South African small, medium, and micro enterprises (SMMEs) feel the pressure of harsh economic conditions and increasing competition. Meanwhile, the country's social media use is growing exponentially. This offers SMMEs the opportunity to transact through Facebook commerce (f-commerce), a low-cost, widely accessible, and potentially profitable sales platform. Utilizing the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as a framework, this study investigates South Africans' perceptions of the ease of use and usefulness of f-commerce and how these perceptions translate into attitudes, intentions, and actual f-commerce use. Data was collected from adult Facebook users via an online self-administered survey using convenience and snowball sampling. Structural equation modeling confirms the suitability of the TAM and its proposed relationships, except for the relationship between usefulness and intention. This study contributes to the limited empirical research on f-commerce adoption in a developing country and provides insights for SMMEs to utilize f-commerce as a sales platform.

Keywords: F-commerce, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, Technology Acceptance Model

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Introduction

The rising internet access, smartphone ownership, and social media use in emerging markets, such as South Africa, are transforming how consumers shop (Broeder 2021). South Africans are increasingly active on social media and use these platforms to shop (Dos Santos & Duffet 2021). Facebook, South Africa's second most popular social media platform, presents marketers and local businesses with an opportunity through Facebook commerce (f-commerce). F-commerce, which refers to the buying and selling of products and services on Facebook (Jamil 2023), is an emerging method of commerce that combines social networks and electronic commerce (e-commerce) in a simple yet effective way, offering a low-cost and potentially profitable sales platform to especially smaller enterprises (Liébana-Cabanillas et al. 2019). Such social media marketing tools have become useful for small businesses to improve their overall

business performance (Doughty & Rambocas 2022). South African small, medium, and micro enterprises (SMMEs), which contribute significantly to job creation and poverty alleviation, are under immense financial pressure (Sibiya et al. 2023). It could potentially benefit from f-commerce as a platform on which to sell their products and services, boost their profits, stimulate overall economic growth and ultimately aid the relief of the unemployment in South Africa. f-commerce, a commission-free, cost-effective, and widely accessible sales platform, allows SMMEs to tap into the growing local and global Facebook user community (Dos Santos & Duffet 2021).

But is f-commerce a viable avenue for SMMEs to market their products and services? Would South Africans be willing to shop on Facebook? What affects their intention to use this platform to acquire products and services? And how do their intentions translate into action? Prior research has investigated consumers' intentions to use f-commerce (Wang et al. 2022, Wiese 2021) and their actual f-commerce use (Husnain et al. 2025); however, limited research is available on the intention of consumers to use f-commerce and their actual use of f-commerce in the context of a developing country, such as South Africa, particularly as it relates to Facebook Marketplace and Facebook Buy and Sell Groups. Furthermore, researchers often fail to use the term 'f-commerce consistently' and its associated concepts. For instance, the terms f-commerce and Facebook shopping (f-shopping) are used interchangeably (Wiese 2021). Additionally, while some researchers argue that f-commerce encompasses transactions that occur solely on Facebook (Brock et al. 2011), others consider transactions initiated on Facebook but conducted elsewhere (whether offline or on an external e-commerce site) to be part of f-commerce as well. Multiple studies fail to specify whether they investigate on-Facebook or off-Facebook f-commerce (Lai et al. 2021, Wang et al. 2022).

Considering the growth of social media use in South Africa, despite the varying levels of digital literacy (Ndulu et al. 2022), the commercially beneficial opportunities offered by f-commerce to SMMEs, the lack of research on the antecedents of f-commerce adoption, and the failure of past research to clearly distinguish between and investigate the various sub-types of f-commerce individually, the purpose of this study was to investigate South African Facebook users' intention to adopt f-commerce as well as their actual f-commerce use, specifically that of Facebook Marketplace and Facebook Buy and Sell Groups. Using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as a framework, we sought to understand consumer perceptions regarding the ease of use and usefulness of f-commerce, whether these perceptions could predict user attitudes toward f-commerce, consequent intentions to utilize f-commerce, and finally, whether these intentions predicted actual f-commerce use.

This article is structured as follows: first, the relevant literature concerning f-commerce, the TAM, and its constructs are reviewed, whereafter, the study's methodology is discussed, and results are interpreted. Lastly, the theoretical and managerial implications of the findings are discussed, limitations are acknowledged, and recommendations for future research are made.

Literature Review

Electronic commerce (e-commerce), which refers to the buying and selling of products and services over the Internet (Feng 2024), offers numerous benefits to small businesses, including global reach, cost-effectiveness, and the ability to compete with larger corporations (Turban et al. 2018). Social commerce (s-commerce), a subset of e-commerce, involves using social media platforms, such as Facebook, to facilitate transactions and interactions. Unlike e-commerce, s-commerce facilitates social interactions and the contribution of user-generated content, promoting the online trade of products and services (Ali et al. 2024). F-commerce refers to conducting e-commerce transactions—such as the sale of products and services—via Facebook (Jamil 2023). F-commerce can take place either as *on-Facebook* or *off-Facebook*. On-Facebook f-commerce refers to buy-and-sell transactions that occur directly on the Facebook platform through Facebook Shops. In contrast, off-Facebook f-commerce refers to buy-and-sell

transactions facilitated on Facebook (via Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups) but occur elsewhere, whether in-store or on an external e-commerce site (Gajewski 2013). Facebook Marketplace, introduced in 2016, is a location-based online marketplace that connects consumers with businesses and other consumers in specific geographical communities, allowing them to trade items with each other. Facebook Marketplace enables buyers and sellers to connect and communicate, facilitating the payment and delivery of items without charging a commission (Abdullahi et al. 2023). Off-Facebook f-commerce can also be conducted through Facebook Buy and Sell Groups, where user-generated content serves as the basis for commercial activities (Chen et al. 2016). These groups are typically formed with a specific audience, location, or product category in mind, allowing members to list items for sale, mark them as sold, and search for items to purchase. Thus, many individuals join these groups to build social relationships and buy and sell items amongst each other. The term f-commerce encompasses the use of various platforms, both on and off Facebook, to trade products and/or services. For the purpose of this study, however, f-commerce refers to the buying and/or selling of products and/or services using Facebook Marketplace and/or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups.

Theory

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was first introduced by Davis (1986) and seeks to model user acceptance of information technologies. According to the TAM, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of a technology determine an individual's intention to use that technology (Venkatesh 2000). Perceived ease of use refers to "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort" (Davis 1989), and perceived usefulness is "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance" (Davis 1989) or productivity (Venkatesh 2000). The TAM also proposes that an individual's perceived ease of use influences their perceived usefulness, as the easier it is to use a technology, the more useful it is perceived to be (Venkatesh 2000). Furthermore, the model suggests that attitude towards a behavior mediates the relationship between internal beliefs (ie perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness) and behavioral intention and that the perceived usefulness of a technology has a direct relationship with an individual's intention to use that technology. Lastly, the TAM suggests that an individual's behavioral intention determines their actual use of technology (Davis et al. 1989).

Thus, according to the TAM, Facebook users will have positive feelings towards using f-commerce platforms when they are perceived as easy to use and beneficial to improving the individual's shopping efficiency. Furthermore, Facebook users are more likely to use f-commerce platforms when they have positive feelings toward them or when they believe these platforms will enhance their shopping efficiency, despite having negative feelings about shopping on Facebook. Lastly, Facebook users' intention to shop using f-commerce platforms will influence their actual use. The TAM has been extensively used to model user acceptance of various technologies (Venkatesh 2000), including the adoption of e-commerce (Ruiz-Herrera et al. 2023) and s-commerce (Khan et al. 2023). This suggests that the TAM is a robust model for predicting user acceptance of online commerce technologies such as f-commerce. Figure 1 shows the variables connected in this study.

Hypotheses Development

Perceived ease of use is the degree to which a Facebook user believes that using f-commerce platforms will be effortless, and perceived usefulness is the extent to which a Facebook user believes that using f-commerce platforms will enhance their shopping efficiency. The perceived ease of use of e-commerce sites (An et al. 2023) and s-commerce platforms (Cutshall et al. 2022) has been found to positively affect a consumer's perceptions of the usefulness of these technologies. Thus, individuals perceived these

technologies as more useful when they required less effort to use them. Given that F-commerce is a type of s-commerce, essentially providing e-commerce functionalities on social networking sites (Jamil 2023), a similar relationship could also be true within an f-commerce context. Furthermore, Facebook claims that its Marketplace platform is fast and simple to use, enabling users to shop in less time. As a result, these shoppers may perceive the platform as more useful, as it improves their shopping efficiency. Thus, as proposed by TAM and based on the above, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H1. Perceived ease of use has a positive influence on the perceived usefulness of f-commerce.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework and the Path Coefficients

Source: the authors

A person's attitude toward a behavior refers to the extent to which an individual feels positively or negatively about performing that behavior (Ajzen 1991). Within the research context, a Facebook user can thus either like or dislike the idea of shopping on Facebook. Research has shown that individuals have more favorable attitudes towards adopting e-commerce technologies (Khasanah et al. 2023, Liu 2024) when they perceive these technologies as easy to use. Since f-commerce offers e-commerce functionalities on social networking sites (Jamil 2023), these relationships may also apply to users' attitudes toward f-commerce. Many South African consumers and micro and small enterprises are still navigating digital retail and may view traditional e-commerce websites as complex or too risky. However, given the high adoption rate of social media and Facebook, they might perceive f-commerce as more user-friendly, as they are already familiar with Facebook. Thus, as proposed by TAM and based on the above, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H2. Perceived ease of use has a positive influence on attitude toward f-commerce.

Research has shown that individuals have a more positive and favorable attitude toward adopting e-commerce when they perceive these technologies as useful (Ashraf et al. 2014). This was confirmed in the context of a mobile banking payment app, where perceived usefulness directly affected consumers' attitudes toward use (Prastiawan et al. 2021). Furthermore, the TAM model suggests that attitude towards a behavior mediates the relationship between internal beliefs (ie perceived usefulness) and intention (Davis et al. 1989). For many South African consumers and SMMEs, especially in digitally marginalized communities, attitudes towards digital platforms such as f-commerce will depend on the perceived value they might derive, such as time-saving, lower cost, ease of access, low entry barriers (especially for micro-enterprises) and increased access to products and services—especially in areas with limited brick-and-

mortar retail options. In a developing country context, these dynamics are even more relevant given South Africa's increasing engagement with digital platforms despite socio-economic inequalities. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H3. Perceived usefulness has a positive influence on attitudes toward f-commerce.

The perceived usefulness of e-commerce has been found to directly influence an individual's intention to adopt these technologies (Khasanah et al. 2023). Individuals are thus more inclined to use these technologies when they are perceived as useful. Because f-commerce offers e-commerce functionalities on social networking sites (Jamil 2023), this relationship may also be applicable in the f-commerce context. Especially in South Africa, where varying levels of digital literacy are evident, leveraging users' familiarity and trust with Facebook will enhance perceived usefulness and intention to use. Lower levels of digital literacy are often associated with skepticism and mistrust, which can have a negative impact on intention; however, familiarity with social media can mitigate this effect. One could thus argue that the intention to use f-commerce in South Africa will be reinforced by the convenience of mobile transactions and the low cost and risk associated with f-commerce (eg usefulness). In a country such as South Africa, where there are economic inequalities, the simplicity and accessibility of f-commerce may positively contribute to the intention to use it, especially for SMMEs. Thus, based on the TAM, as well as the above, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H4. Perceived usefulness has a positive influence on the intention to use f-commerce.

Furthermore, an individual's attitude toward adopting e-commerce has been found to influence an individual's intention to adopt these technologies (Liu 2024). According to the TAM, an individual's attitude toward performing a particular behavior is thus viewed as a precursor to their intention to perform the actual behavior (Davis et al. 1989). Such behavioral intentions refer to the probability that an individual will perform a specified behavior and indicate the amount of efforts people are willing to exert to accomplish it (Ajzen 1991). South Africans seek convenience and affordability, and Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups offer a soft transition between traditional retail and digital retailing. Given South Africa's increased mobile use, positive attitude toward mobile transactions, and growing acceptance of social media and Facebook as a commercial space, it is hypothesized that:

H5. Attitude has a positive influence on the intention to use f-commerce.

Generally, the more intent an individual is on performing a behavior under their volitional control, the more likely they are to perform that behavior (Ajzen 1991). This is also true for e-commerce adoption (Chakraborty et al. 2022, Hoang & Tung 2023). Given that f-commerce provides e-commerce functionalities on Facebook (Jamil 2023), intention might also be positively linked to behavior in the f-commerce context. This trend is also observed in South African e-commerce, where consumer willingness to engage in online shopping has increased alongside improvements in digital infrastructure and mobile penetration. The fact that f-commerce provides e-commerce functionalities within Facebook offers a low-barrier entry point for South African consumers and SMMEs to online shopping, as lower levels of digital literacy are often observed in developing countries. In addition, the intention to use f-commerce could be driven by economic necessity. Given South Africa's high unemployment rate, both individuals and SMMEs may consider selling products via f-commerce as an alternative stream of income and an additional distribution channel. Thus, based on the TAM and the above, the following hypothesis was formulated.

H6: Intention to use f-commerce has a positive influence on f-commerce use

Methodology

The study population consisted of Facebook users who had been active on the platform within the 30 days preceding data collection and were at least 18 years of age. Focusing on Facebook as a commerce platform is relevant since it is the most widely used social network in South Africa, second only to WhatsApp (Klonaridis & Lues 2023). Since no sampling frame exists for South African Facebook users, non-probability convenience and snowball sampling were used. Although studies testing similar constructs in a similar context utilized sample sizes of 200 and 400 respondents (Liébana-Cabanillas et al. 2019), we aimed for a sample size of over 500 to counteract non-response bias associated with non-probability sampling. A sample of 549 respondents was realized. However, given the nature of non-probability convenience and snowball sampling, where no clear sampling frame exists and where we do not know the number of people invited, it isn't easy to calculate a response rate. After receiving ethical clearance, the researcher pre-tested the survey and made minor adjustments based on feedback received. The questionnaire was uploaded to Qualtrics, an online survey platform, and distributed using a link posted and shared on Facebook. Individuals were incentivized to participate through an entry into a lucky draw. Screening questions confirmed that respondents were adult Facebook users (18 years and older) who had accessed Facebook within 30 days prior to completing the questionnaire. Scales measuring perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, attitude, and behavioral intention were adapted from Hernández-García et al. (2011). Items were reworded to fit the f-commerce context, specifically the Facebook Marketplace and Facebook Buy and Sell Groups context. Perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, attitude, and behavioral intention were each measured using three items on a seven-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree, and 7=strongly agree), and f-commerce use was measured using a dichotomous scale (1=yes and 2=no). The last section of the questionnaire collected respondents' demographic information, including their gender and age.

Sample Characteristics

A total of 549 respondents participated in this study. Most respondents were female (77%) and aged between 25 and 34 years (34%). People integrate Facebook into their everyday lives, as most respondents (94%) use Facebook daily and have been using it for more than five years (93%). Furthermore, most respondents (70%) had used Facebook Marketplace and/or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups to buy and/or sell products or services in the past.

Analysis and Results

In accordance with the process suggested by Malhotra et al. (2020), two models were run: First, a measurement model (CFA) to confirm validity and reliability; and second, a structural model (SEM) to test hypotheses. To assess validity and reliability, the fit of a measurement model (CFA) was assessed (Kline 2023); it showed an acceptable model fit with $CMIN=3.68$, $RMSEA=.07$, $CFI=.98$, $IFI=.98$. As can be seen in Table 1 all Cronbach's alpha (CA) coefficient values and composite reliability (CR) values were above .7, indicating convergent validity. The AVE values were all above .5. Further, the square roots of the AVE values were greater than the correlations among the constructs, indicating discriminant validity (Hair et al. 2021). After confirming validity and reliability, a structural model (SEM) was run, showing an acceptable model fit with $CMIN/DF=1.63$, $RMSEA=.04$, $CFI=.91$, $IFI=.92$. Figure 1 shows the path coefficients.

Table 1. Validity and Reliability

	Measure item (Hernández García et al. 2011)	Mean	SD	CA	CR	AVE
	Perceived ease of use	1.90	.89	.83	.74	.50
PEOU1	I think it's easy to buy and sell on Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups	1.95	1.09			
PEOU2	I think that using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups is easy to learn for me	1.78	.93			
PEOU3	I think that using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups is easy to use to shop	1.95	1.04			
	Perceived usefulness	2.40	1.21	.88	.79	.57
PU1	I think that using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups allows me to shop in less time	2.28	1.31			
PU2	I think that using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups allows me to improve my shopping efficiency	2.61	1.46			
PU3	I think that using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy-and-Sell Groups to shop is useful for me	2.30	1.25			
	Attitude	2.22	1.08	.90	.85	.65
ATT1	I like the idea of using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups to shop	2.32	1.29			
ATT2	I think that using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy-and-Sell Groups to shop is a good idea	2.19	1.18			
ATT3	I think that using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups is a smart idea	2.14	1.11			
	Intention	2.12	1.13	.91	.87	.70
INT1	I have the intention to use Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups in the future	2.13	1.30			
INT2	I am likely to shop using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups in the future	2.20	1.30			
INT3	I will consider the idea of using Facebook Marketplace or Facebook Buy and Sell Groups in the future	2.02	1.10			
	F-commerce use		YES		NO	
	Have you ever used Facebook Marketplace or a Facebook Buy-and-Sell Group to buy or sell a product or service?		70%		30%	

Discussion

The study's results indicate that f-commerce presents a potentially profitable platform for local SMMEs struggling with the challenges of harsh economic conditions, intense competition, and high unemployment rates. Secondly, the results highlight perceived ease of use, usefulness, attitude, and intention as antecedents of f-commerce adoption. Thirdly, the results validate the TAM as a model for understanding f-commerce adoption in a developing country context such as South Africa, given that five of the six hypotheses were accepted.

In line with previous research (An et al. 2023, Cutshall et al. 2022), the findings of this study indicate that respondents' perceived ease of use predicts their perceived usefulness of f-commerce. Thus, the more straightforward and user-friendly individuals and SMMEs find the Facebook Marketplace, the more useful it will be. For SMMEs, it may increase their usefulness in terms of time and effort in marketing and

selling their products, while for individuals, it presents a convenient way to shop. Further, supporting previous research (Khasanah et al. 2023, Liu 2024), the results of this study indicate that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness predict attitudes toward f-commerce. The results confirm that perceived usefulness best predicts attitude toward f-commerce. It is evident that for South African Facebook users and SMMEs, positive attitudes towards Facebook Buy and Sell groups and Facebook Marketplace, for example, are shaped by the practical benefits (usefulness) and minimal effort (ease of use). It also highlights that although developers should ensure that digital technologies are user-friendly, the value derived from these technologies will ultimately have the most impact on users' attitudes. Consistent with previous studies, the results indicate that attitude is a significant predictor of intention (Khasanah et al. 2023, Liu 2024). The result highlights that South Africans' feelings about f-commerce drive intention; thus, improving how SMMEs; for example, feel about f-commerce is crucial for growing its adoption in South Africa.

However, in contrast to previous studies (An et al. 2023, Cutshall et al. 2022), the results show that perceived usefulness does not significantly ($p=.87$) predict f-commerce intention; the relationship is also negative. This suggests that just because technology such as f-commerce is useful is not enough to ensure intent. The negative relationship, although not significant, is counterintuitive. Possible explanations are that the risks of being scammed outweigh the usefulness of f-commerce, or it is a psychological pushback against perceived pressure to use f-commerce. It is also possible that, although useful, f-commerce does not meet the shopping or distribution preferences of SMMEs or individuals, such as those who prefer social interaction when going to or selling at a flea market rather than relying solely on it. However, more research is needed to uncover the possible reason(s) for the result. Finally, the findings of this study reveal that respondents' intention to use f-commerce predicts their actual use of f-commerce. This finding aligns with previous research, which has demonstrated a positive correlation between intention and use (Chakraborty et al. 2022, Hoang & Tung 2023). This is good news, especially for SMMEs, as consumers who intend to use Facebook's buy-and-sell groups or Marketplace are very likely to follow through and shop on these platforms. This is reassuring, as often the reality is an 'intention-behavior gap' as intentions are not always backed by behavior – even if a theory such as TAM posits it to be true. This result provides ease of mind for SMMEs considering f-commerce as an alternative distribution channel.

Theoretically, this study contributes to limited empirical research on the antecedents of f-commerce adoption, particularly within a developing country context. Furthermore, this study focuses on adopting specific f-commerce *off-Facebook* platforms (Facebook Marketplace and Facebook Buy and Sell Groups) that facilitate transactions. Still, the transactions don't take place on Facebook itself. Past research has largely failed to investigate the various f-commerce subtypes individually, instead adopting a generic approach to examine f-commerce adoption (Al Amin et al. 2024).

Implications for Managers

From a practical perspective, developers of f-commerce platforms, marketing managers, and SMMEs should note that when an individual perceives an f-commerce technology as easy to use and useful, they are more likely to have a positive attitude toward using that f-commerce platform. Perceived usefulness is a stronger predictor of attitude, and f-commerce developers who wish to foster positive consumer feelings toward their platforms should thus ensure that f-commerce platforms help Facebook users shop more efficiently before ensuring the platform is easy to use. Unlike the developers of f-commerce platforms, marketing managers and SMMEs cannot modify the f-commerce platform's usability and functionalities to make it easier to use and more useful. They can educate consumers on how to use these platforms effectively, which could improve user perceptions regarding the ease of use and usefulness of f-commerce. This may foster positive attitudes and intentions toward using f-commerce, ultimately increasing consumers' likelihood of shopping on Facebook. Furthermore, marketing managers and

SMMEs can stimulate f-commerce use by incentivizing Facebook users to shop using Facebook Marketplace and Facebook Buy and Sell Groups. Sales promotions can significantly influence purchasing behavior among consumers. Price promotions, such as discounts, may enhance consumers' perceptions of value, while loyalty programs can increase purchase intention. Marketers and SMMEs can thus utilize these tools to encourage Facebook users to adopt f-commerce. By utilizing f-commerce, these consumers might become more accustomed to shopping on Facebook and perceive f-commerce as easy to use and useful. This, in turn, will lead to more positive attitudes toward and intention to shop using f-commerce in the future. F-commerce is a viable avenue for SMMEs to market their products and services, as South Africans are willing to shop on Facebook, especially when the f-commerce platform is easy to use and helps improve shopping efficiency. South Africans are thus moving away from using Facebook only as a platform for social interactions and toward using it for transactions.

Limitations and Direction for Future Research

This study has some limitations that need to be recognized. Firstly, the study employed non-probability convenience and snowball sampling, implying that its findings are limited to the study's respondents and cannot be generalized to a broader population, with the associated limitations of non-response bias. Future studies should investigate the antecedents of f-commerce behavioral intention and adoption under more study populations. Secondly, this study only examined the TAM and its constructs (perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, attitude, and behavioral intention) as antecedents of f-commerce use. Future research could investigate the effect of other predictor variables on individuals' intention to use and actual use of f-commerce and explore which condition could lead to a negative relationship between perceived usefulness and use intention, as found in this study. For example, trust plays a crucial role in influencing online shopping behaviors (Wang et al. 2023). The same might be true for f-commerce platforms, such as Facebook Marketplace and Facebook Buy and Sell Groups. Fear of missing out (FOMO) may also drive consumers' choices of digital payment systems they use (Wati et al. 2024); therefore, f-commerce platform developers should ensure they offer all the latest digital payment options to retain customers. Lastly, this study only investigated the adoption antecedents of two off-Facebook f-commerce platforms: Facebook Marketplace and Facebook Buy and Sell Groups. Future studies could investigate the adoption antecedents of on-Facebook f-commerce platforms such as f-stores.

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